

Deliverable 3.3.1.1

LIST OF REQUIRED SUBSTITUTE DATA

30.12.2024

D3.3.1.1 List of required substitute data

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General Information

Summary

The involvement of the industry is an important building block for the successful development of community services for energy system research. On the one side, industry partners can contribute with technical as well as business-related data sets. On the other side, industry partners can also access data or services provided by the NFDI4Energy.

However, the data that can be shared by individual industry partners might not be complete. For example, grid data such as topology or line parameters is often not available. Personal data, such as household energy consumption may only be shared after anonymization process.

Therefore, it is required to analyze which data has to be substituted. This deliverable will analyze the requirements of the industry regarding the need for substitute data. For this purpose, information from literature review and an online survey has been collected.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Figure 1 Task Area 3 connections to other Task Areas within the NFDI4Energy consortium

D3.3.1.1. builds on earlier tasks in TA3, especially: M3.1, which identified industry requirements. Task 3.2.1. developed a process for sharing and using FAIR data. This deliverable is a part of M3.3. Its outcomes serve as input to TA4 (FAIR research data) and TA5 (Simulation in Interdisciplinary Energy Research) once the requirements have been satisfied. This deliverable comprises the following tasks:

- Analyze the requirements of the industry regarding the need for substitute data.
- Split substitute data into two categories:
 - Missing data, that has to be substituted by synthetically created data.
 - Personal data, that has to be processed and replaced by anonymized data.

This work ensures that the services remains functional and useful, while respecting privacy and data availability constraints.

1 Introduction

The main objective of this deliverable is to gather information on the requirements for substitute data in energy research, as a part of NFDI4Energy project. To achieve this goal, this deliverable is divided into two sections:

- The first section analyses these requirements through a literature review. First, it describes the reasons for the need for substitute data in energy research. This is followed by the types of required substitute data within this domain. Finally, it discusses how missing values can affect energy research.
- The second section is the results of an online survey titled “Requirements for Substitute Data in Energy Research Services” that was conducted and shared with several participants from the NFDI4Energy consortium and researchers working with energy-related data.

The collected information from both sections can be used in the future to develop tools for generating synthetic data and anonymizing personal data.

2 Identifying Required Substitute Data (Literature Review)

2.1 Need for Substitute Data in the Energy Domain

In the energy domain, the effectiveness of data-driven applications, for instance demand forecasting relies heavily on the availability of complete and high-quality data. However, data are often affected by missing, incomplete, or unreliable data due to various technical, environmental, and operational factors. To address this challenge, substitute data becomes essential. The reasons for the need to substitute data can be categorized into five main areas: data scarcity, technical challenges, privacy and security concerns, data quality issues, and modeling and research requirements.

- Data Scarcity [1], [2]
 - Limited available datasets
 - Insufficient datasets in the energy domain
 - Manual labelling is costly and infeasible for large datasets
- Technical Challenges [3]
 - Disruption in the data collection process or specific electric power levels are not detected, due to:
 - Unstable synchronous transmission between the sensors and the databases in the network
 - Interruption in communication transmission
 - unreliable communications equipment
 - Low quality of network communication
 - Environmental factors
- Privacy and Security [1], [2], [3], [4]
 - Data can include Personally Identifiable Information (PII), and this demands sophisticated techniques and algorithms to anonymize the data
 - Compliance with regulations and ethical considerations
- Data Quality Issues [2], [5]
 - Lack of high-quality data
 - Low-quality data can lead to imprecise or incorrect predictions by machine learning models.
- Modelling and Research Requirements [1]
 - Machine learning-based models require large-scale datasets for training.

- Insufficient size or scope of datasets limits the application of advanced models, reducing the potential for high-accuracy results.

2.2 Types of Required Substitute Data in the Energy Domain

Generally, there are two types of required substitute data within the energy domain, which can be categorized as the following:

- Missing Data
 - According to [1], fine-grained time series data may be missing at the distribution system level. Therefore, synthetic data which is generated using the Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) method can be used to model the conditional probability distribution of real datasets and maintain privacy.
 - According to [2], generative AI models such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), and Diffusion Models learn the data distribution and samples from the learned distribution to produce novel data objects.
 - According to [4], in cases such as missing data related to medium voltage distribution feeders, a generative algorithm to synthesize realistic feeder characteristics can be applied using identified statistical distributions.
 - According to [3], some parts of the collected data set such as power consumption, voltage, or electric current may be missing for a certain period in electric power data because of facility problems and poor communication, which relate to environmental factors. Generally, two types of missing values exist for a specific time:
 - Single missing values, which can be removed from the original dataset, leading to a complete dataset.
 - Multiple missing values, which is more challenging compared to missing values and requires imputation methods (e.g., K-NN, SVR, ARIMA) to fill in the missing data.
 - According to [5], advanced deep learning techniques such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and transfer learning techniques are applicable in filling missing values for building energy data.
- Personal Data
 - According to [1], to protect privacy in datasets containing energy consumption and user-specific data known as Personally Identifiable Information (PII) is removed or obfuscated.
 - According to [2], techniques like data masking, data perturbation, and differential privacy can be used to anonymize sensitive energy datasets such as customer consumption data.

2.3 Impact of Missing Data on Energy Research

According to the literature, energy research can be affected by missing values from different perspectives:

- Forecasting Accuracy
 - Missing data can reduce the ability to train machine learning models effectively.
 - Lack of complete data reduces the robustness and accuracy of results.
- Data Integrity
 - Ignoring or removing missing data can result in a loss of valuable information, which could affect the analysis and decision-making processes in energy management.

- Model Performance
 - Incomplete datasets make it challenging to evaluate the model performance
 - Missing data, especially in large-scale datasets, can disrupt the continuity of data, leading to reduced accuracy and generalization ability of machine learning and AI models.
- Bias in Analysis
 - If missing data is not handled properly, it can introduce bias into the analysis, skewing results and affecting the fairness or validity of energy consumption studies.
- Limitations in Data usage
 - The absence of certain data points can limit the scope of research and the application of advanced analytical techniques that rely on comprehensive datasets.

3 Identifying Required Substitute Data

An online survey titled “Requirements for Substitute Data in Energy Research Services” was conducted with participants from the NFDI4Energy consortium and researchers working with energy-related data. The survey included 24 questions divided into three sections, (1) Identify Required Substitute Data, (2) Requirements for Synthetic Data Generation, (3) Anonymization of Personal Data.

A total of 37 responses were collected from individuals representing various organizations, including RWTH, OFFIS, Fraunhofer FIT, FAU, and the University of Freiburg. Respondents held diverse roles such as researchers, group leaders, chief engineers, doctorate candidates, software developers, and team leaders. Over half of the participants reported having 1 to 5 years of experience in the field of energy data.

3.1 Identify Required Substitute Data

Q3.1.1. What types of data are most commonly missing from industry datasets you work with?

Based on 19 survey responses, grid topology data is the most commonly missing type, affecting 57.89% of respondents. This is followed by load profiles (52.63%) and generation profiles (47.37%), indicating that consumption and production pattern data are frequently unavailable. Line parameters data gaps affect 42.11% of respondents. Beyond traditional power system data, 10.53% of respondents mentioned other types of missing data, including operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT) topology data, as well as multi-energy system data such as heating and cooling loads. These results indicate that industry datasets face completeness issues across multiple areas.

Figure 2 Most common types of missing data from industry datasets

Q3.1.2. What types of personal data do you encounter in your datasets?

Based on the survey responses, individual load profiles are the most encountered personal data type, appearing in 9 cases (40.91% of total encounters). This is followed by total energy consumption data in 7 cases (31.82%) and generation profiles in 4 cases (18.18%), indicating that energy-related personal information dominates industry datasets. User demographics appear least frequently, found in only 2 cases (9.09%). No respondents reported encountering other types of personal data beyond the four surveyed categories. These results show that consumption and generation pattern data represent the primary personal data privacy concerns in power system datasets, while demographic information remains relatively uncommon in operational data collections.

Figure 3 Types of Personal Data Identified in Datasets

Q3.1.3. What data formats do you most commonly work with?

Based on the survey responses, CSV is the predominant data format, used by 17 respondents (50% of completed responses). JSON follows as the second most common format with 9 users (26.5%), while XML is used by 5 respondents (14.7%). Additionally, 3 respondents reported working with other data formats beyond the main categories. Among the detailed responses, participants identified several specialized formats including SQLite for database storage, CIM CGMES (Common Information Model Common Grid Model Exchange Standard) for power system data exchange, and Excel for spreadsheet-based data handling.

Figure 4 Most used data formats

3.2 Requirements for Synthetic Data Generation

Q3.2.1. What is the extent of missing values in your data? Do you have an estimate of the percentage of missing values for different variables or data sets?

Based on the survey responses, the answers are as follows:

- Missing data ranges from 5% to 60%, depending on dataset type (e.g., pilot sites, aggregated data).
- Missing or erroneous data is often detected only during prolonged disconnects (days to weeks).
- Aggregated data (e.g., total consumption) may mask granular missing values, complicating analysis.
- Pilot sites and similar sources report up to 60% missing values, indicating significant gaps in availability.
- In some cases, entire datasets are unavailable, further impacting research efforts.

Q3.2.2. Do you have insights into the reasons why data may be missing? Are there specific factors or conditions that contribute to missing values?

Based on the survey responses, limited access to data and privacy of data are equally significant factors, each affecting 8 cases. Scale of data presents challenges in 3 cases, while 6 respondents cited other reasons for missing values. These findings indicate that access restrictions and privacy concerns are major barriers to complete datasets. Beyond the structured categories, respondents identified several operational and technical issues contributing to missing data:

- Restricted access to certain datasets contributes significantly to missing values.
- Large-scale datasets are prone to missing data due to complexity and handling challenges.
- Data privacy concerns and the criticality of certain information restrict its availability.
- Missing data can originate at the provider level due to incomplete datasets or operational issues.
- Missing values often result from malfunctioning measurement devices or sensor errors during data collection.
- Power or communication outages further contribute to data gaps.

Figure 5 Reasons why data may be missing

Q3.2.3. How do missing values affect your ability to analyse and derive insights from the data? Are there particular analyses or research questions where missing values pose significant challenges or limitations?

Based on the survey responses, the answers are as follows:

- Modeling Limitations:
 - Missing data poses significant challenges in modeling heat demand at the building level and impacts urban-scale planning tasks.

- It limits the ability to build models for cyber-physical power systems, including grids and process networks.
- Reduced Analytical Detail:
 - Missing values constrain the granularity and depth of analyses, affecting the level of insights derived.
- Challenges in Real-Time Applications:
 - Missing close-to-real-time data (e.g., from ENTSO-E) disrupts services dependent on these datasets, requiring fallback solutions.
 - The issue is less severe for historic datasets, where gaps are often addressed.
- Machine Learning and AI Limitations:
 - Supervised deep learning tasks, especially for advanced models, are heavily affected, requiring large and complete datasets for effective training and validation.
 - Missing data complicates representative studies and validation of new tools or algorithms.
- Increased Manual Effort:
 - For tasks like forecasting, extended missing periods require manual data cleaning, increasing resource requirements and complexity.
- Application-Specific Challenges:
 - Applications such as ML-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and forecasting suffer from missing values, which reduce their reliability and efficacy.

Q3.2.4. Do you see potential for using synthetic data as a substitute for real data in your research? If yes, what are the key parameters or inputs needed to generate synthetic data for your research?

Based on the survey responses, the answers are as follows:

- General Potential:
 - Most respondents see potential for synthetic data as a substitute, though with varying levels of confidence and specific conditions.
- Key Parameters and Inputs:
 - Building-level inputs: Insulation, construction year, and other physical properties for simulating heat consumption.
 - Process network inputs: Generic architectures and grid topologies for modeling synthetic process networks.
 - Behavioral and device-level inputs: Detailed knowledge about individual behavior and device usage is critical but challenging to model.
- Conditions for Effectiveness:
 - Synthetic data must be tailored to individual situations, to be effective.
 - Physical simulation could enhance relevance by replicating complex, realistic behaviors more effectively than deterministic approaches.
- Challenges:
 - Synthetic data struggles to capture the nuanced "real-world effects" observed in actual datasets, which are often critical for validation.
 - Deep learning models rely heavily on realistic data to demonstrate their ability to recognize complex patterns, making overly deterministic synthetic data less valuable.
- Alternative Approaches:

- Some prefer using open datasets from similar contexts to replace missing values instead of generating synthetic data.

Q3.2.5. How do you validate the accuracy and reliability of synthetic data?

Based on the survey responses, the answers and some problems are as follows:

- Lack of Experience:
 - Some respondents noted they had not engaged in validating synthetic data, highlighting a gap in experience or necessity.
- Validation Methods:
 - Testing against complete datasets: Algorithms generating synthetic data are validated by applying them to known, complete datasets to compare results.
 - Data Unit Tests: Structured unit tests are used to evaluate specific aspects of synthetic data accuracy and reliability.
 - Visual Inspection: Data is reviewed manually to assess whether it appears realistic and aligns with expectations.
- Effectiveness Based on Context:
 - Validation quality depends significantly on the effort and methodology used during synthetic data creation.
 - Synthetic data for certain contexts, such as network topologies, is considered reliably valid by some respondents.
- Challenges:
 - Trust in source: Some respondents rely on the credibility of the synthetic data's source rather than direct validation.
 - Reliance on real data: There is skepticism about the ability to validate synthetic data fully, with a preference for confirming results against real-world data.

Q3.2.6. What features would you like to see in a synthetic data generation tool?

Based on the survey responses, customization options are the most sought-after feature, requested by 9 respondents (45% of completed responses). User-friendly interface follows as the second priority with 6 requests, while integration with other tools was mentioned by 4 respondents. Additionally, 2 respondents specified other feature requirements beyond the main categories. Among the detailed responses, participants emphasized the need for validation of results to ensure better reliability and high-resolution data generation capabilities. These findings suggest that industry professionals prioritize flexibility and customization in synthetic data tools, while also valuing ease of use and quality assurance features to meet their specific analytical and operational requirements.

Figure 6 Expected features in synthetic data generation tool

Q3.2.7. Can you recommend any existing tools for synthetic data generation? Please provide names and details

Based on the survey responses, there is limited awareness and adoption of existing synthetic data generation tools among respondents. Out of 12 total responses, 10 participants provided no answer, while 2 gave specific feedback. One respondent acknowledged having no knowledge of synthetic data generation tools, indicating a knowledge gap in the field. Another respondent mentioned two specific tools: OpenSynth [6] and richardsonpy [7] but noted that neither tool fully meets their specific requirements, e.g. high resolution.

3.3 Anonymization of Personal Data

Q3.3.1. What are the key parameters or inputs that need to be anonymized for your research?

Based on the survey, key parameters or inputs that need to be anonymized are as follows:

- Personal and Sensitive Information:
 - Customer information: Key parameters for anonymization include customer names and locations, especially in load profile data.
- Load and Generation Profiles:
 - Load and generation data for individual customers, particularly in low-voltage (LV) distribution grids, would need anonymization to prevent identification.
- Business-Sensitive Data:
 - Business-sensitive information, such as customer names, is commonly anonymized to protect confidentiality in research.
- Minimal Use of Personal Data:
 - Some respondents indicated that their work does not involve personal data directly, but they've encountered anonymized data from research partners in the past, where business-related information was anonymized.

Q3.3.2. Which anonymization techniques do you currently use?

Based on the survey responses, aggregation is the most used anonymization technique. Pseudonymization and suppression are each used by 1 respondent, while 2 respondents reported using other anonymization methods beyond the standard categories. Among the detailed responses, one participant described receiving only generic, high-level data as an anonymization approach, such as obtaining state or zip code information instead of exact addresses for electric load monitoring locations. Another respondent indicated they use no anonymization techniques. These findings suggest that anonymization practices in the power systems industry vary significantly, with some

organizations relying on data generalization rather than formal anonymization methods, while others may not implement anonymization protocols at all.

Figure 7 Anonymization techniques in use

Q3.3.3. How do you ensure that the anonymized data cannot be re-identified?

Based on the survey, the answers are as follows:

- Anonymization by Project Partners:
 - In many cases, data is already anonymized by project partners, reducing the need for further intervention.
- Aggregation:
 - Results are aggregated over large datasets, such as hundreds of simulations or users, ensuring that individual data points cannot be traced back to specific entities.
- Non-Publication of Personal Data:
 - Personal data is not published, which further ensures that any potentially identifiable information is not exposed.

Q3.3.4. What challenges do you face in anonymizing data?

Based on the survey, the answers are as follows:

- Delays in Data Access:
 - Obtaining anonymized data can cause significant delays, as the process of anonymization or acquiring already anonymized data takes time.
- Uncertainty in Data Sharing Agreements:
 - There is often uncertainty about user consent and what users have agreed to when sharing their data. Lack of clear agreements leads to cautious handling, as the terms of data usage and sharing are not always transparent.

Q3.3.5. What features would you like to see in a data anonymization tool?

Based on the survey responses, ease of use is the most requested feature for data anonymization tools, mentioned by 6 respondents (37.5% of completed responses). Effectiveness follows as the second priority with 5 requests, while compliance with regulations was cited by 4 respondents. The results indicate that industry professionals prioritize user-friendly interfaces and practical effectiveness in anonymization tools, suggesting that current solutions may be overly complex or cumbersome to use.

Figure 8 Expected features in the data anonymization tool

Q3.3.6. Can you recommend any existing tools for data anonymization? Please provide names.

Based on the survey responses, there is no tool recommendations for data anonymization.

Q3.3.7. What are the key parameters or inputs that need to be anonymized for your research?

Based on the survey, key parameters or inputs that need to be anonymized are as follows:

- Personal and Sensitive Information:
 - Customer information: Key parameters for anonymization include customer names and locations, especially in load profile data.
- Load and Generation Profiles:
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- Minimal Use of Personal Data:
 - Some respondents indicated that their work does not involve personal data directly, but they've encountered anonymized data from research partners in the past, where business-related information was anonymized.

Q3.3.8. Which anonymization techniques do you currently use?

Based on the survey responses, aggregation is the most used anonymization technique. Pseudonymization and suppression are each used by 1 respondent, while 2 respondents reported using other anonymization methods beyond the standard categories. Among the detailed responses, one participant described receiving only generic, high-level data as an anonymization approach, such as obtaining state or zip code information instead of exact addresses for electric load monitoring locations. Another respondent indicated they use no anonymization techniques. These findings suggest that anonymization practices in the power systems industry vary significantly, with some organizations relying on data generalization rather than formal anonymization methods, while others may not implement anonymization protocols at all.

Figure 9 Anonymization techniques in use

Q3.3.9. How do you ensure that the anonymized data cannot be re-identified?

Based on the survey, the answers are as follows:

- Anonymization by Project Partners:
 - In many cases, data is already anonymized by project partners, reducing the need for further intervention.
- Aggregation:
 - Results are aggregated over large datasets, such as hundreds of simulations or users, ensuring that individual data points cannot be traced back to specific entities.
- Non-Publication of Personal Data:
 - Personal data is not published, which further ensures that any potentially identifiable information is not exposed.

Q3.3.10. What challenges do you face in anonymizing data?

Based on the survey, the answers are as follows:

- Delays in Data Access:
 - Obtaining anonymized data can cause significant delays, as the process of anonymization or acquiring already anonymized data takes time.
- Uncertainty in Data Sharing Agreements:
 - There is often uncertainty about user consent and what users have agreed to when sharing their data. Lack of clear agreements leads to cautious handling, as the terms of data usage and sharing are not always transparent.

Q3.3.11. What features would you like to see in a data anonymization tool?

Based on the survey responses, ease of use is the most requested feature for data anonymization tools, mentioned by 6 respondents (37.5% of completed responses). Effectiveness follows as the second priority with 5 requests, while compliance with regulations was cited by 4 respondents. The results indicate that industry professionals prioritize user-friendly interfaces and practical effectiveness in anonymization tools, suggesting that current solutions may be overly complex or cumbersome to use.

Figure 10 Expected features in the data anonymization tool

Q3.3.12. Can you recommend any existing tools for data anonymization? Please provide names.

Based on the survey responses, there is no tool recommendations for data anonymization.

3.4 Summary of survey

Table 1 presents a summary of the two principal data categories requiring substitution. Missing Data represents non-personal technical data that is frequently unavailable in industry datasets, with Grid Topology Data being the most critical gap. The missing data encompasses essential technical information including network infrastructure details, energy consumption and generation patterns at aggregated levels, electrical system specifications, and multi-sectoral energy system data. These gaps significantly impact researchers' ability to conduct comprehensive power system analysis and modelling. Personal Data represents sensitive information that requires anonymization or synthetic replacement to protect individual privacy while maintaining analytical value. Individual Load Profiles represent the most encountered personal data type. This category highlights the tension between data utility and privacy protection, as these datasets contain valuable behavioural and usage patterns but pose significant privacy risks if not properly handled.

Table 1 List of required substitute data

Missing Data	Grid Topology Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network structure and connectivity information • System architecture data
	Load Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated consumption patterns • Non-personal energy usage data
	Generation Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated generation patterns • Non-personal renewable energy production data
	Line Parameters Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrical characteristics of transmission/distribution lines • Network component specifications
	Operational Technology (OT) and Information Technology (IT) Topology Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System integration and communication network data • Control system architectures
	Multi-Energy System Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heating system data • Cooling system data • Cross-sector energy flows
Personal Data	Individual Load Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer-specific consumption patterns • Granular usage data

	Total Energy Consumption Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer-specific total consumption • Individual billing-related energy data
	Customer Generation Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual renewable generation data • Prosumer production patterns
	User Demographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer names and locations • Customer information from load profile data • Business-sensitive customer information

Based on the survey results from Task 3.3.1, several key insights can inform the development of Task 3.3.2 Develop tools for the creation of synthetic data and Task 3.3.3 Develop tools for the anonymisation of personal data:

- CSV as Date Input Format

According to answers about [Q3.1.3. What data formats do you most commonly work with?](#), CSV is the most used data format, the synthetic data generation and anonymization tools can prioritize CSV compatibility to ensure maximum usability and adoption in industry applications. Supporting additional data formats, such as JSON and XML, is an advantage.

- Synthetic Data Validation

According to [Q3.2.5. How do you validate the accuracy and reliability of synthetic data?](#), survey responses highlight limited experience with synthetic data validation and varying approaches, including dataset comparison, unit tests, and visual inspection. Validation effectiveness depends on context and data generation methods. Future tools can include synthetic data validation and use visualizations to show differences between synthetic and real data.

- Relationship Between Data Anonymization and Synthetic Data Generation

Anonymized data can serve as the basis for training models that generate synthetic data. Moreover, synthetic data can help address missing values in anonymized datasets. Additionally, it can replace sensitive information to enhance privacy protection and data utility.

4. Conclusion

Research on energy benchmarking models is being actively pursued to assess energy performance and identify inefficiencies. However, data collection is challenging, and specialized knowledge and time are required posing challenges.

Research in the field of energy primarily focuses on handling missing data in time-series data, such as energy consumption data. Missing data in a time series significantly impacts model performance owing to disrupted data continuity, making it a critical research topic in the energy sector. However, most studies provide unclear definitions of missing data. This is because missingness in time-series data is often handled using model-based approaches that focus on identifying patterns in missing data rather than the causes of missingness.

Identifying and defining the causes of missing data beforehand plays a crucial role in understanding the dataset and developing future synthetic data generation or anonymization strategies.

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